
The Syntactic Function of *Gembira*: A Corpus-Based Study

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Abstract

A bare-form adjective can place the function of predicate, complement, and adverb in a sentence. This is a description of how the adjective of *gembira* syntactically functioned in a clause. To define it, a deep theoretical understanding is required as a qualitative approach. So, this is a descriptive qualitative study. Downloading the data from Leipzig Corpora and transferring the data to Antconc then analyzing it in Ms. Excel, the analysis defined the following results: (1) bare-form adjective of *gembira* is mostly used as a modifier in the number of 78 times or 84%, it modifies the nouns such as *kabar*, *berita*, *wajah*, and *suasana*, (2) there are 15 times function as predicate. The results of the analysis explained that the bare-form adjective of *gembira* in the Indonesian language is in universal characteristics as exemplified by the languages of Manange, Jarawara, and Qiang as explained by Carol and Dixon. Moreover, morphologically, the adjective *gembira* in its bare form is merely similar to Manange to Jarawara and Qiang. Syntactically, the meaning of the adjective *gembira* is identified according to the phrase structure and clause word order which is also determined in the language of Manange, Jarawara, and Qiang.

1. Introduction

A word explicates the form of a language: phonologically or grammatically (Aikhenvald, 2007). The phonological word establishes meaning mainly through prosodic changes, such as in Mandarin

and any Sino-Tibetan language. On the other side, grammatical words establish the meaning of language by the morphological processes of affixation, compounding, and reduplication (Katamba, 1993; Lieber, 2009, Aronoff & Fudeman, 2011). The grammatical word establishes not only the meaning but also the grammatical function or relation through the morphological processes, specifically the inflectional affixation (Haspelmath, n.d.; Stewart & Stump, 2001). The inflectional affixation, for the agglutination language (Haspelmath, 2014; Haspelmath & Anthropologie, 2000; Plank, 2014) Demonstrated the function and relation of nominal, verbs/predicate, and modifier (Marneffe et al., 2021). The grammatical and syntactical functions expounded the relations due to the meaning of the noun, verb, and adjective. According to the universal dependency, the nominal is built by the noun, while the predicate is built by the verb, however, the modifier is built by the adjective, the noun phrase, and the prepositional phrase. In short, the adjectives, in many languages, commonly demonstrated the meaning and function of a modifier.

Moreover, the formation of words in every language is defined differently by their structure and meaning, which is again, semantically defined as nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, and other grammatical words that syntactically function as subjects, predicates, complements, objects, and adverbs (Dixon & Aikhenvald, 2003). However, due to their meaning, Dixon stated that words are potentially semantically overlapping, such as adjectives that semantically attributed nouns and show comparison. Still, it is also possible syntactically can be an adverb, a complement, and also as a predicate (Dixon & Aikhenvald, 2003). To observe the realization of this semantic overlapping, this article shows some examples of the adjective semantic overlapping, affecting the syntactic function in Manange, Jarawara, and Qiang.

Manange is a language that is spoken in the Himalayas-Nepal. The report of the analysis of the language defined that there are two types of adjectives, namely (1) simple adjectives and (2) verb-like adjectives or verb-adjectival. As Dixon defined, which also happened in Manange, ideas of expressing color, speed, and quantification are only expressed by a simple adjective, and then ideas of expressing difficulties and human propensity are expressed by verb-like adjectives. Look at some examples below:

Simple Adjectives such as:

<i>1mleŋkya</i>	'black-color'
<i>3kini</i>	'fast-speed'
<i>2katti</i>	'too many-quantification'

Verb-like adjectives such as:

<i>4kyokro</i>	'old-age/human propensity'
<i>1sē</i>	'young-age/human propensity' – <i>1sē</i> = a process become young
<i>3kathe</i>	'thin-size/human propensity'
<i>2mre</i>	'fat-size/human propensity' <i>2mre</i> = a process become fat

The existence of verb-like adjectives in Manange created a syntactic function of the adjective as a predicate. Look at the following example:

<i>2phi=ko</i>	<i>1piŋkya</i>	(Manange: Carol & Christine, 2004: 86)
Top=DEF	blue	
*Top blue 'The top blue'		

The word *1piŋkya* 'blue' has an overlapping semantic function; it is a verb-like adjective that expresses a condition, probably sadness or happiness. As a verb-like adjective, *1piŋkya* is not meant as a blue color but a process of bluish. Then the sentence 'the top blue' means 'the top turned into sadness', so *1piŋkya* in the sentence is an intransitive verb function as a predicate. This overlapping

syntactic function is sourced from the semantic overlapping of verb-like adjectives. In Manange, the adjective is an adjective like verb in bare form. The adjective become an adjective like verb because of the function in a clause as a predicate.

Another adjective phenomenon came from the Jarawara language. This language is spoken by the Amazonians, and it has a very small type of adjective. There are two unique things about the adjective in this language: (1) the existence of copula-based gender, for example, *ama-ke* for female and *ama-ka* for male, this copula is used to express the adjective existence. Then (2) the adjective in Jarawara implicitly defined the meaning of the verb or adjective-like verb. and since the copula is based on gender, it turned like an auxiliary in the sentence, but it is not; the adjective is. Look at the following example:

Bani amosa-bote ama-ka (Jarawara: Dixon, 2004: 189)
 Animal(m) be.good-very be.declarative (m)
 *animal very good
 'The bird is very pretty'

The focus is on the words *amosa-bote*, which are meant as *amosa* 'be good' and *-bote* 'very'. The word *amosa* is an adjective-like verb because there is a meaning of 'be' that links the subject *Bani* to the adjective *amosa-bote*. However, Jarawara must complete the sentence with the copula-based gender of *ama-ka* 'be' to identify that the subject is a male. The copula of *ama-ka* and *ama-ke* were the lexical which signaled the reader or listener that the clause is build by an adjective as the predicate. The function of an adjective as a predicate in Jarawara language turned the adjective into an adjective like-verb.

The last language in this article to show the adjective phenomenon came from the Qiang language. Qiang is a Tibetan National language in China. It is an agglutinative language. The syntactic word order is ended by a verb. It is also both a head and dependent marking language. Lapolla defined the adjectives of Qiang as 5 syntactic functions: (1) as a predicate, (2) as a head of NP, (3) as a modifier of a noun, (4) as an adverbial modification, and (5) as an adverbial phrase. In this study, the function of Qiang will be explained as Qiang is the (1) predicate function and (2) adverbial function. Look at another example below:

Pie-le ba-ji (Qiang: Lapolla, 2004: 309) Pig-
 DEF: CL big-CSM
 *The pig big
 'The pig is bigger'

The sentence in Qiang shows how the adjective *ba-ji* with its CSM (change of state marker) in its *-ji* can turn into a verb that is semantically equal to 'grows'. In the sentence, the adjective *ba-ji* 'big', which is syntactically a predicate, changed the state into a verb, so the meaning of the sentence '*pie-le ba-ji*' is 'the pig grows' or 'the pig is getting bigger'. The adverbial function of an adjective is shown as the following:

The: na-ji mo-su (Qiang: Lapolla, 2004: 319)
 3sg good-ADV NEG-study
 *She good not study
 'She doesn't study well'

The sentence in Qiang shows the existence of *na* 'good' as an adjective, and by the addition of *-ji*,

the adjective of *na* was changed into *na-ji* or 'well'. In this example, it was clearly defined that the Qiang language has a syntactic function of adverb for an adjective by the addition of *-ji* to the adjective. Unlike, the language of Manange and Jarawara, Qiang has a morphology system that determines an adjective as a predicate which is in the form of grammatical morphemes of *-ji*. The existence of affix *-ji* directly signaled the reader or listener about the clause which is predicated by an adjective.

One popular adjective in the Indonesian language is *gembira* 'happy', which is synonym to *senang* and *bahagia*. The popularity of *gembira* is identified by the composition of words compounding it. Compared to Manange, Jarawara, and Qiang languages, this study wants to define the syntactic function of *gembira* in its bare form. Due to the explanation of adjectives in Manange, Jarawara, and Qiang, adjectives in Manange and Jarawara are mainly used in their bare form, and Qiang is mainly used in the affixation by corpus-based analysis. This study wants to define whether *gembira* of the Indonesian language is merely like the Manange and Jawaara or Qiang.

2. Materials and Methods

As a corpus-based analysis, the data analyzed are downloaded from the Leipzig Corpora of Indonesian News in 2022. The corpus data that are chosen are the 300 thousand sentences of capacity, which are totally in 4.646.888 words by the corpus of News. The sentences which are downloaded were imported to Antconc tools and arranged according to the hits of the adjective of *gembira*. From 300 thousand sentences, there are 93 sentences with the hit of *gembira*, which were arranged with the left and right context of the hit. The 93 sentences with the hit of *gembira* were then imported to Ms. Excel to be analyzed. In the Ms. Excel, the sentences were analyzed by identifying the hit into its syntactic function of adjective, predicate, complement, and adverb. The analysis can be observed directly by clicking the following [link](#). However, according to the focus study, data acquired, and findings, this study is a descriptive qualitative study (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Soegiyono, 2011)

3. Results and Discussions

The Analysis explicated the results, which are deeply explained in the part of the discussion. The results exemplified the realization of the syntactic function of the adjective *gembira*, including its collocation. The following are the explanation of the results and followed by its discussion. The 93 sentences with the hit of *gembira*, which is displayed in Ms. Excel, are then analysed, and finally, the following results of each syntactic function amount are found:

Function	Amount	(%)
Modifier (In Subject, Object, Predicate, and Complement)	78	84
Predicate	15	16
Total	93	

Table 1. The amount distribution of *gembira* syntactic function

The Adjectives of Gembira as Modifiers

The table above shows that more than 50% of the bare form adjective of *gembira* is used as an adjective or attributing the other words. In addition to that, the further analysis defines that the bare form of adjective *gembira*, which is attributed to other words, is attributing (1) noun, (2) adverb, and (3) adjectives in word compounding. Look at the examples below

1. *Rasa gembira menyelimuti-nya*
 Feel.NOUN happy.ATR surround.PRED-him.CLIT
 *Feel happy covers her.
 'The happiness surrounded her'
2. *Pihak kejaraan bahkan tidak mengumumkan kabar gembira*
 Side.ADJ palace.NOUN even.CONJ not.NEG declare.VERB news.NOUN ADJ
 *Side palace even not declare news happy
 'The palace side event didn't declare the happy news'
3. *Mudah-mudahan menjadi berita gembira, tadas-nya*
 Hopefully.ADV be.PRED news.NOUN happy.ADJ said.Rep. word – him.CLIT
 *Hopefully be news happy, said he 'Hopefully, it becomes a happy news, he said'
4. *PKS menyatakan ingin membawa suasana gembira*
 PKS.name said.PRED want.verb ATR bring.PRED situation.NOUN happy.ADJ
 *PKS said want bring situation happy
 'PKS said that they want to bring a happy situation'
5. *Raut wajah gembira ter-lihat pada-nya*
 Expression.NOM face.NOUN happy.ADJ looked.PRED on.PREP-nya-CLIT
 *Expression face happy looked on him 'The
 happy face is expressed on him'

On those sentences above, there are clear descriptions of how the adjective *gembira* functions as a noun attribute for the nouns *rasa*, *kabar*, *berita*, *suasana*, and *wajah*. The next function of *gembira* as an adjective is the attribute of adverb (modifying adverb), by the following structure:

Mereka berkumpul bersama dengan begitu gembira
 3.PL.PRON sit.PRED together.ADJ with.COP so.ADV happy.ADJ
 *They sit with so happy
 'They sit together with so happy'

Those sentences show the function of the adjective *gembira* in modifying the adverb of *begitu*. The next adjective *gembira* structure is attributing another adjective in adjective word compounding, such as the following:

Riang gembira
 Happy.ADJ happy.ADJ

Sorak gembira
 Happy.ADJ happy.ADJ

Gembira ria
 Happy.ADJ happy.ADJ

The sentences defined the structure of the adjective *gembira* as attributes for nouns, adverbs,

conjunctions, and other adjectives in word compounding. The next function of the adjective *gembira* is a modifier for verb; the corpus data defined this function as the following:

Mereka merasa gembira karena kejadian itu
 3.PL.Pron feel.Pred happy.Compl because.Conj event.Noun DET
 *They feel happy because of the event that 'They
 feel happy because of that event'

Based on the sentence above, it is clear that *gembira* is completing the information of the subject *mereka* 'they'. In this clause, the adjective *gembira* functioned as a direct modifier for the verb. However, there is also a function of the adjective *gembira* which indirectly modifies the verb. Look at the following clauses:

1. *Mereka merayakan upacara itu dengan gembira*
 They:Pron celebrated:PRED ceremony:Noun DET with:COP happy:ADJ
 *They celebrated the ceremony with happy 'They
 celebrated that ceremony happily

2. *Bantuan itu disambut gembira oleh seluruh warga desa*
 Help.Noun DET PASS.welcome.Pred happy:ADJ by all.ADJ people.Noun village.Noun
 *Help that welcomed happy by all people village 'That
 helps are welcomed happily by the villagers'

The indirect function of the adjective in modifying the verb is determined by the position which is the last in the clause. Those sentences above define the function of the bare-form adjective *gembira* as a modifier for the predicate. In the first sentence, it is used to modify the celebration of a ceremony and then continued to the second as a way of how the process of welcoming happened.

The Adjective Gembira as a Predicate

The next syntactic function of *gembira*, which is found in the corpus-based analysis, is as a predicate. The corpus-based analysis also defined the bare-form adjective of *gembira* as having a syntactic function of the predicate. Look at the data below:

1. *Dia gembira karena kelahiran kedua anak itu*
 3SG.Pron happy.PRED because.CONJ birth.Noun two.QUANT child.Noun DET
 *He happy because birth two child that
 'He is happy because of the birth of the two children'

2. *Ibu Ana Fauziah sangat gembira bisa bertemu Erlangga Hartanto*
 Name (f) very:ADV happy:ADJ can:AUX meet:PRED name (m)
 *Mrs. Ana Fauziah very happy can meet Mr. Erlangga Hartanto 'Mrs. Ana
 Fauziah was very happy can meet Mr. Erlangga Hartanto

3. *Anak-anak itu selalu gembira dan tidak pendendam*
 Kids.PL DET always:ADV happy:ADJ and.Conj.not.NEG revengeful:ADJ
 *Children that always happy and not revengeful
 'Those children are always happy and not revengeful'

On those sentences, the bare-form adjective of *gembira* functions as words that mainly define the ideas of the sentence or as a predicate. The first sentence is *gembira* by a condition, then for the second sentence is *gembira* because of meeting someone, and the last *gembira* by telling the characteristics of children. Those are the functions of adjectives in their bare form to give the main ideas of the sentences.

The analysis of the adjective *gembira* defined two functions in clauses they are (1) as modifiers for nouns in subject and object, adverbs in complement, and verbs in verb phrase, and (2) as a predicate. Similar to the language of Manange, Jarawara, and Qiang, the adjective of *gembira* in the Indonesian language also can function not only as a modifier but a predicate. However, the functioning of the *gembira* in clauses both as a modifier and predicate happened in its bare form. To sum up, look at the clause below:

- | | |
|--|---------------------|
| 1. <i>Dia bernyanyi dengan <u>wajah gembira</u></i>
3SG.she sings CONN face happy
'She sings with a happy face' | Modifying noun |
| 2. <i>Mereka berjalan dengan <u>riang gembira</u></i>
3PL.they walk CONN glad happy
'They walk happily' | Modifying adjective |
| 3. <i>Dia bernyanyi dengan gembira</i>
3SG.she sings CONN happy
'She sings happily' | Modifying verb |
| 4. <i>Ibu gembira karena kedatangan kami</i>
Mother happy because arrival us
'Mother feels happy because we came' | As a Predicate |

Sentences 1 to 4 exemplified the function of the adjective *gembira* in clauses. The findings of the *gembira* function in clauses demonstrated the other position of an adjective (specifically for *gembira*) in the Indonesian language which is similar to the other languages (Manage, Jarawara, Qiang) that is an adjective-like verb. Moreover, the function of the adjective *gembira* as a predicate happened as a semantic overlapping. In this discussion, the Indonesian through the adjective *gembira* determines its uniqueness from the adjectives in the languages of Manange, Jarawara, and Qiang. The determination is identified through the similarities and differences from the points of (1) form (morphology), and (2) meaning in clause (syntax).

Morphologically, the adjective of the Indonesian language can function as a predicate in its bare form and without any lexical addition which is similar to the adjective in the language of Manange. Its function in bare form is different from the language of jarawara which morphologically needs the addition of lexical *ama-ka* and *ama-ke* in signaling the clause which is adjectival predicated. However, the bare form of the adjective in the Indonesian language is also different from the language of Qiang which the adjective is suffixed by *-ji*.

Syntactically, the meaning of *gembira* is determined by its position whether as a modifier or a predicate. As a modifier, the adjective *gembira* is positioned after the head for both nouns, adverbs, and verbs. This position indicates the structure of phrases in the Indonesian language which is left-headed. Furthermore, the function as a predicate is identified by its position after the subject. In short, the adjective function as a modifier and a predicate in a clause is purely determined by its meaning as it is required by a speaker or writer to build a clause that ends up with the structure of a phrase and

words order of a clause. The identification of the meaning of an adjective is also according to the word order in a clause for the languages of Manange, Jarawara, and Qiang.

4. Conclusion

The explanation of the adjectives in the language of Manange, Jarawara, and Qiang exemplified the function of the adjectives which is not only as a modifier for the nouns, adverbs, or verbs but also semantically as a predicate. This is universally determined as it is also realized in the adjective of the Indonesian language. Through the word *gembira*, the Indonesian language is defined use the adjective for two functions (1) as a modifier for the nouns, adverbs, and verbs, and (2) as a predicate which identified the adjective as an adjective like verb.

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